

Full-Core Neutronics Calculations using TRIPOLI-4.12[®] for the NuScale-like SMR and BEAVRS 4-Loop PWR

Romain Garat¹, Yi-Kang Lee^{1*}, François-Xavier Hugot¹

¹Université Paris-Saclay, CEA, Service d'Études des Réacteurs et de Mathématiques Appliquées
91191 Gif-sur-Yvette, France

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803811

ABSTRACT

The TRIPOLI-4.12[®] Monte Carlo radiation transport code has recently been released to the NEA Data Bank. To verify and validate its application on full-core reactor physics calculations, benchmark studies were conducted for the NuScale-like small modular reactor (SMR) and the BEAVRS 4-Loop PWR. A comparative analysis of the benchmark data for the two cores was first conducted. Various native geometry modeling methods, input and output (I/O) data verification modules, code simulation options, and nuclear data libraries were employed. The calculation results were compared with published data obtained using the Serpent 2.2.0 and MVP3 Monte Carlo radiation transport codes. For the NuScale-like core, comparisons were made for key reactor physics parameters, including K_{eff} , control rod worths (RE1, RE2, SH3, SH4, and all control banks combined), and radial and axial power distributions. For the BEAVRS benchmark, the Hot Zero Power (HZP) All Rods Out (ARO) case was analyzed using the same native combinatorial geometry approach. Multiple nuclear data libraries were tested, including ENDF/B-VII.1, ENDF/B-VIII.0, JEFF-3.1, JEFF-3.3, and JEFF-4.0. The benchmark results demonstrated good agreement among TRIPOLI-4.12[®], Serpent 2.2.0, and MVP3, confirming TRIPOLI-4.12[®]'s capability for high-fidelity, full-core reactor physics analysis.

Keywords: TRIPOLI-4[®], Criticality mode, JEFF-4.0, NuScale-like SMR, BEAVRS PWR benchmark

1. INTRODUCTION

TRIPOLI-4[®] is the fourth-generation Monte Carlo radiation transport code developed by the Reactor Physics and Applied Mathematics Division (SERMA) at CEA Paris-Saclay [1–3]. The TRIPOLI-4[®] version 12 code is now available through the NEA Data Bank [4]. To verify and validate this version of the TRIPOLI-4[®] code [2], along with its I/O data visualization tool T4G [3] and associated nuclear data libraries, full-core neutronics calculations were performed for two benchmark reactor systems: the NuScale-like small modular reactor (SMR) [5,6] and the BEAVRS 4-Loop PWR [7–9].

With the growing interest in small modular reactors (SMRs) as potential sources of low-carbon energy, NuScale represents one of the most mature SMR designs and is the first to be certified by the U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission [5]. The published neutronics benchmark for the NuScale-like core is well defined and documented, with reference calculation results available from the Serpent 2.2.0 Monte Carlo neutronics transport code [6].

For the BEAVRS benchmark problems, measured data from a commercial-scale reactor core are available [7-9]. The BEAVRS benchmark is based on an actual 4-Loop PWR nuclear power plant, using detailed geometry and material specifications to construct a comprehensive neutronics calculation model. This benchmark currently provides the most detailed set of specifications among all openly available LWR full-core benchmarks [8]. For the Hot Zero Power (HZP) BEAVRS cases, reactor physics benchmark calculations have recently been published using the MVP3 Monte Carlo code [8, 9].

*Email address for primary/corresponding author: yi-kang.lee@cea.fr

The TRIPOLI-4[®] code has been applied to full-core neutronics calculations for more than 30 years. Early applications include fuel depletion analyses of the CEA ORPHEE research reactor [10] and the simulation of the 2001 Dampierre PWR fuel loading incident at EDF [1]. Over the years, numerous developments have been incorporated into the code. In this study, the native combinatorial geometry with fuel lattice options was selected to construct detailed pin-by-pin full-core models. Mesh tally detectors were employed to obtain radial and axial power distributions, while the T4G visualization tool was used to verify geometry cells, material assignments, and mesh tally outputs. The temperature interpolation and probability table options were employed to ensure accurate use of the nuclear data and to improve the treatment of unresolved resonances in configurations with inserted control rods.

2. NUSCALE-LIKE SMR AND BEAVRS 4-LOOP PWR

A general comparison between the NuScale-like core and the BEAVRS core is presented in Table I. These fundamental parameters are essential for TRIPOLI-4[®] modeling and for conducting neutronics verification and validation (V&V) calculations.

Table I. Comparison of NuScale-like SMR and BEAVRS PWR full-core benchmark data used in TRIPOLI-4[®] Monte Carlo transport verification and validation calculations

Benchmark	NuScale-like core [5, 6]	BEAVRS core [7-9]
Reactor type	PWR (SMR)	PWR (4-Loop)
Reactor Power (MWth)	160	3411
Fuel assembly number	37	193
Active fuel height (cm)	200	365.76
Fuel pin/assembly pitch (cm)	1.2598 / 21.5036	1.25984 / 21.50364
Fuel pin per assembly	264 (17 × 17 lattice)	264 (17 × 17 lattice)
Fuel enrichment (wt% U235)	1.5, 1.6, 2.5, 2.6, 4.05, and 4.55	1.6, 2.4, and 3.1
Fuel pellets	UO ₂ and UO ₂ + Gd ₂ O ₃	UO ₂
Fuel pellet / pin radius (cm)	0.4058 / 0.4750	0.39218 / 0.45720
Boron in coolant water	1000 ppm	975 ppm (ARO)
Control rod absorber	B4C (upper) + AIC (lower)	B4C (upper) + AIC (lower)
Control rod assembly bank	RE1, RE2, SH3, and SH4	A, B, C, D, SA, SB, SC, SD, and SE
Burnable poison (BP)	64 UO ₂ -Gd ₂ O ₃ rods in 4 C02 fuel assemblies (4.55 wt% U235)	1266 Borosilicate glass rods in core (12.5 wt% B ₂ O ₃)
Heavy reflector	Yes (17.82 cm 304L SS + Coolant)	No
Pressure Vessel radius (cm)	Only core barrel data 93.98 / 99.06	219.71 (int.) / 241.30 (ext.)
Core temperature	900 / 600 K (Fuel / Coolant)	566 K (Hot Zero Power state)
Reference calculations	Serpent 2.2.0 (ENDF/B-VII.1)	MVP3 (JENDL-4 & 5)

The NuScale-like SMR features a smaller core, characterized by a reduced number of fuel assemblies (37) and active fuel height of 2 m. This design results in higher neutron leakage from the fissile zone compared to the BEAVRS PWR. From the viewpoint of neutron economics, this increased leakage can be mitigated by introducing a heavy reflector for the NuScale-like SMR (see Table 1 and [6]). A second approach to compensate for the high neutron leakage and to sustain core criticality and fuel cycle length is to enhance neutron production within the fuel region by employing higher-enriched fuel assemblies. In the NuScale-like SMR, two types of such assemblies—C01 and C02—contain 4.05 wt% and 4.55 wt% U-235 enrichment, respectively (see Fig. 1 and Table I).

Figure 1. NuScale-like Core loading pattern and control rod assembly locations. All dimensions are in cm. [6].

However, the use of higher-enriched fuels not only increases fuel fabrication and electricity generation costs but also introduces local power peaks and imposes operational constraints on the reactor. To mitigate radial power peaking, the C01 and C02 fuel assemblies were placed in the peripheral regions of the NuScale-like SMR (see Fig. 1). These fuel assemblies introduce the heterogeneous radial power distribution and increase the local uncertainties of calculated neutron flux and fission rates in the neutron transport calculations.

Figure 2. BEAVRS Core cross-section including radial structures and enrichment loading pattern. Black denotes steels for Pressure Vessel, Neutron Shield Panel, Core Barrel, and Baffle, and red, yellow, and dark blue denote the 1.6, 2.4, and 3.1 wt% U235 fuel assembly regions, respectively [7, 8].

Figure 2 shows the BEAVRS core loading pattern, including the control rod assembly banks (A, B, C, D, etc.) on the left, and the number of burnable poison rods per fuel assembly on the right. The BEAVRS PWR core consists of 193 fuel assemblies with an active fuel height of 365.76 cm. The core features three U-235 enrichments and nine control rod banks (see Table I). The Hot Zero Power (HZP) condition was considered, with a coolant boron concentration of 975 ppm and an inlet coolant temperature of 566 K [7, 8]. The All Rods Out (ARO) case was first evaluated in this study using several nuclear data libraries.

3. TRIPOLI-4® CALCULATIONS AND RESULTS

To model the TRIPOLI-4® full-core reactor physics calculations, native geometry options were tested, including the combinatorial geometry, surface-based geometry, and a mixed approach combining both. These models were verified and validated to assess calculation performance and user workload during geometry data implementation. Among them, the native combinatorial modeling approach proved to be the most efficient choice. Lattice structures for 17×17 fuel pins and “lattice-of-lattices” configurations for fuel assembly models—7×7 for the NuScale-like core and 15×15 for the BEAVRS core—were implemented using the RESC operators. The visualization and diagnostic tools T4G [3], CHECK_GEOM, CHECK_TRACKING, and SCAN_GEOMCOMP modules [2] were routinely employed in a step-by-step process to identify and correct geometry errors during model development.

To verify the input material composition data, including material density, mass, and volume, the CALCULATION module was employed for validation. Table 3 in reference [6] lists the nuclide compositions of all fuel types; however, the data for the C02 fuel (4.55 wt% U-235) are not correct. After verification of the fuel density and fissile mass, the revised data of C02 fuel were found from the benchmark website [6]. Nuclear data are temperature-dependent and the TEMPERATURE_INTERPOL option was a user-friendly feature for applying temperature-dependent nuclear data in the simulations.

For the power map calculations, the EXTENDED_MESH tally option was applied to fission rates at the fuel pin, fuel assembly, and full-core levels [11]. The power map data calculated by TRIPOLI-4® were stored in output files, which could then be automatically and interactively loaded and visualized using the T4G tool together with the predefined full-core geometry model [3]. To treat the source convergence, the PACKET_LENGTH option was employed with 200 active cycles after rejection of inactive cycles.

Table II. TRIPOLI-4® calculated results for full-core neutronics parameters of NuScale-like SMR

NuScale-like SMR (see Fig.1) Core state	Keff (σ in pcm)			Control rods worth (CRW) (σ in pcm)		
	TRIPOLI-4 Version 12	Serpent 2.2.0 [6]	$\Delta \rho$ (pcm)	TRIPOLI-4 Version 12	Serpent 2.2.0 [6]	Δ CRW (pcm)
All rods out	1.02838 (5)	1.02768 (1)	66	n/a	n/a	n/a
RE1 in	1.00791 (9)	1.00723 (1)	67	-1974 (10)	-1975 (2)	1
RE2 in	1.00378 (9)	1.00313 (1)	64	-2383 (10)	-2381 (2)	2
SH3 in	0.99042 (9)	0.98978 (1)	66	-3727 (10)	-3726 (2)	1
SH4 in	0.99045 (9)	0.98971 (1)	75	-3724 (10)	-3733 (2)	9
All rods in (SCRAM)	0.85853 (5)	0.85791 (2)	84	-19238 (6)	-19255 (2)	17
	0.85559 (8) [PT* absent]		-317	-19638 (9) [PT* absent]		383

* PT: Probability Table for Unresolved Resonance Region (URR) cross-section treatment.

3.1. TRIPOLI-4® models and calculation results for NuScale-like core

The NuScale-like core loading pattern and control rod assembly banks shown in Fig. 1 were modeled and reproduced using TRIPOLI-4®, as illustrated in Fig. 3 using the T4G display tool (left: native surface-based geometry model including core barrel; right: native combinatorial geometry model, showing only seven fuel types and the surrounding reflector region). Both the heavy reflector and the core barrel were explicitly modeled for both geometry models. Using the ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data library, the TRIPOLI-4® calculation results are presented in Table II and Figs. 4–6.

Table II presents the K_{eff} values and control rod reactivity worths (CRW) for the control rod assembly banks RE1, RE2, SH3, SH4, and the all-rods-in (SCRAM) cases. Overall, good agreement was achieved between the results obtained using the Monte Carlo codes TRIPOLI-4® version 12 and Serpent 2.2.0 for these benchmark cases. As the neutron energy spectrum becomes harder in the control-rod-inserted and SCRAM configurations, the Probability Table option for Unresolved Resonance Region (URR) cross-section treatment proved useful in improving the benchmark consistency.

The observed reactivity differences (ranging from 64 to 101 pcm \pm 9 pcm) in Table II may be attributed to differences in nuclear data processing and neutron tracking methods between the two codes. Figure 4 compares the normalized core power maps at the fuel assembly level, showing an average deviation of approximately 0.17% between TRIPOLI-4® version 12 and Serpent 2.2.0 calculations.

Figure 3. TRIPOLI-4® models of NuScale-like core (Left: Native surface-based geometry model, Right: Native combinatorial geometry model, only showing the seven fuel types and the reflector). Radial structures include 18.72 cm thick heavy reflector and 5.08 cm thick core barrel.

Figure 4. TRIPOLI-4® calculated NuScale-like core power map in fuel assembly level using native combinatorial lattice (CE) [4, 11]. This power map was benchmarked against the Serpent 2.2.0 calculations [6]. The average difference between TRIPOLI-4® and Serpent in fuel assembly level is around 0.17% with maximum Monte Carlo standard deviation of 0.3%.

Figure 5. TRIPOLI-4[®] calculated NuScale-like core power map in fuel pin level (Left) and its uncertainty map (Right). The pin power peaks appear near the peripheral fuel assemblies C01 and C02 (see Fig. 1) where the U235 enrichment levels are higher, 4.05 and 4.55 wt%, respectively. Owing to the Gd₂O₃ in 4 C02 fuel assemblies (see Table I and Fig. 1), the power peaking effect in C02 fuel zones is effectively reduced.

Figure 5 presents the TRIPOLI-4[®] calculated core power maps at the fuel pin level for the NuScale-like core. Due to the presence of the higher-enriched C01 and C02 fuel assemblies (see Fig. 1), pin power peaks appear near the peripheral zones of the core. As a result of neutron leakage from the fuel region into the heavy reflector, combined with backscattered neutrons from the reflector, higher pin power uncertainties are observed at the corners of the C01 and C02 fuel assemblies (see Fig. 5 right map).

Figure 6 presents the TRIPOLI-4[®] calculated axial power distribution. Good agreement was achieved when compared with the reported Serpent 2.2.0 results [6]. Each fuel assembly in the NuScale-like core includes five axial grid spacers made of Zircaloy-4 and Alloy 718 (Inconel). Since the exact mass and geometry of these grid spacers are not publicly available, a simplified modeling approach was adopted [6]. The influence of these grid spacers on the axial power profile can be clearly identified in Figure 6.

Figure 6. TRIPOLI-4[®] calculated axial power distribution for NuScale-like core. The exact mass and geometry of fuel assembly grid spacers are not publicly available and a simplified approach was used in the benchmark [6]. The influence of three grid spacers on the axial power profile can be clearly identified.

3.2. TRIPOLI-4® models and calculation results for 4-Loop PWR BEAVRS core

The BEAVRS core loading pattern shown in Fig. 2 was reproduced using TRIPOLI-4®, as illustrated in Fig. 7. In this study, only the ARO case at the Hot Zero Power state was initially modeled to test various modeling options of the TRIPOLI-4® code. To investigate the influence of structural materials, the impact of assumed heavy reflector, and the reactivity worth of burnable poison rods on core criticality, several modeling configurations were developed during this study. Figure 7 presents two of these TRIPOLI-4® models for the BEAVRS core [7, 8]: one representing a bare core without internal radial structures, and the other a full-core model including all radial structural components.

Figure 7. TRIPOLI-4® models of BEAVRS 4-Loop PWR core [7-9]
 (Left: Bare core without radial internal structures, right: Full-core cross-section including radial structures, both were visualized with the T4G tool). Red denotes steels for Reactor Pressure Vessel. Green denotes stainless steel for neutron shield panel, core barrel, and baffle.

Table III presents the TRIPOLI-4® calculated K_{eff} values for the BEAVRS core at the Hot Zero Power state. Five nuclear data libraries were independently employed to benchmark the results against the published MVP3 calculations [8]. Two distinct groups of K_{eff} values were identified. The first group—comprising ENDF/B-VII.1, JEFF-3.1, and JENDL-4—yielded K_{eff} values close to unity (approximately 70 ± 10 pcm higher). The second group—comprising ENDF/B-VIII.0, JEFF-4.0, and JENDL-5—produced K_{eff} results roughly 290 ± 10 pcm above unity. The K_{eff} value obtained with JEFF-3.3 clearly forms a third category.

Table III. TRIPOLI-4 calculated K_{eff} values of BEAVRS PWR core (HZP, All rods out (ARO)) [7, 8])

BEAVRS Core state	Keff (σ in pcm)				
	TRIPOLI-4.12®			MVP3 [8]	
ARO	ENDF/B-VII.1		ENDF/B-VIII.0	JENDL-4	JENDL-5
Hot Zero Power (HZP & 566 K)	1.00074 (8)		1.00291 (8)	1.00077 (2)	1.00292 (2)
	JEFF-3.1.	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-4.0		
	1.00067 (9)	1.00491 (8)	1.00283 (8)		

4. CONCLUSIONS

Full-core neutronics calculations using TRIPOLI-4.12[®] native geometry have been performed for both the NuScale-like SMR and the BEAVRS 4-Loop PWR. The results for key reactor physics parameters showed good agreement with benchmark data obtained from recent Serpent 2.2.0 and MVP3 Monte Carlo neutron transport calculations. Future work will extend these studies to include a power distribution analysis under asymmetric control rod insertion for the NuScale-like core, as well as a detailed evaluation of the control rod bank worths for the BEAVRS core, which are significantly smaller than those of the NuScale-like design. Additional ongoing efforts include modeling the isothermal temperature coefficient (ITC) and analyzing in-core detector responses for the BEAVRS benchmark. Furthermore, an independent analysis of the BEAVRS core with materials temperature set to 600 K instead of 566 K has been conducted using both the TRIPOLI-4[®] ROOT-based geometry model and the new TRIPOLI-5[®] AGORA geometry model [12].

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

TRIPOLI-4[®] is a registered trademark of CEA. The authors acknowledge EDF for partial financial support. The authors thank Dr. Cédric Jouanne for preparing the nuclear data libraries. The first author thanks the financial support from CEA for his 2025 internship stay at CEA-Saclay.

REFERENCES

- [1] J.-P. Both et al., "Tripoli-4, a three-dimensional poly-kinetic particle transport Monte-Carlo code." In *Proceedings of the Int. Conf. on Supercomputing in Nuclear Applications SNA'2003, Paris, France, 22-24 Sep 2003 (2003)*. URL <https://www.osti.gov/etdeweb/servlets/purl/20542421>.
- [2] F.-X. Hugot et al., "Overview of the TRIPOLI-4[®] Monte Carlo code, version 12." *EPJ Nuclear Sci. Technol.* **10**, 17 (2024). URL <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjn/2024018>
- [3] Y.-K. Lee and F.-X. Hugot, "TRIPOLI-4[®] Monte Carlo code verification and validation using T4G tool." *Proceedings of ICONE31*, Aug. 4-8, 2024, ICONE31-135213, Prague, Czech Republic, (2024).
- [4] NEA-1940, "TRIPOLI-4.12, Coupled Neutron, Photon, Electron, Positron 3-D, Time Dependent Monte-Carlo Transport Calculation." URL <https://www.oecd-neo.org/tools/abstract/detail/nea-1940>.
- [5] Y. Sun and K. Kurosaki, "Technical overview of recent developments in Small Modular Reactors in the United States." *Physics and Society (physics.soc-ph)*, Submitted on 3 Apr 2025 (2025). (For NuScale SMR pp. 9-12) URL <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2504.02599>
- [6] E. Fridman, Y. Bilodid, and V. Valtavirta. "Definition of the neutronics benchmark of the NuScale-like core." *Nuclear Engineering and Technology*, **Vol. 55**, pp. 3639–3647 (2023). URL <http://doi.org/10.14278/rodare.2024>.
- [7] N. Horelik, B. Herman, M. Ellis, et al. Benchmark for evaluation and validation of reactor simulations (BEAVRS) RELEASE rev.2.0.2. Cambridge (MA): MIT Computational Reactor Physics Group; (2018).
- [8] M. Suzuki and Y. Nagaya, "Whole core analysis of BEAVRS benchmark for hot zero power condition using MVP3 with JENDL-5." *Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology*, **Vol. 61(2)**, pp. 177–191 (2024). URL <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223131.2023.2279299>
- [9] BEAVRS, URL <https://github.com/mit-crgp/BEAVRS/tree/master?tab=readme-ov-file#readme>
- [10] F. Damian and E. Brun, "ORPHEE research reactor: 3D core depletion calculation using Monte-Carlo code TRIPOLI-4." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **Vol. 82**, pp. 203–216 (2015).
- [11] Y.-K. Lee and F.-X. Hugot, "Use of TRIPOLI-4.5 mesh tally to investigate power maps of the LEU-COMP-THERM-008 PWR critical lattices." *Proc. M&C 2009*, Saratoga Springs, NY, May 3-7, 2009, (2009).
- [12] P. Garces, C. Larmier, and A. Jinaphanh. "Validation of TRIPOLI-5[®] Monte Carlo code using the BEAVRS Benchmark." In PHYSOR 2026. Torino, Italy (2026).